

Multi-annual Programme

science based
risk assessment
and independent
advise on possible
risks for public
and animal health

Multi-annual programme **Office for Risk Assessment**

2007-2011 'New light on risk'

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Foreword

We are proud to present the 2007-2011 Multi-annual Programme of the Office for Risk Assessment of the Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority (VWA). It describes the organisation of the Office and the way it operates in a dynamic environment, along with our vision for the future. We have designed a work programme for research and advise for the coming years based on our own position and trends in our environment. It concerns the pro-active medium -long term component of our work, the unsolicited advise concerning threats to human and animal health and the scientific research required to provide it. Solicited advise is an additional component of our work that is not subject to self tasking.

In developing our vision of the future we consulted national and European experts in our field. In this way we identified the themes which we hope to address in the coming period. These are based on generally recognised trends in the physical and social environment. However, the topics within the themes are clearly related to the remit of the Office for Risk Assessment.

The 2007-2011 multi-annual programme will also form the basis of successive annual plans, which describe in greater detail the tasks facing the Office in the coming year, setting clearer priorities and taking account of international developments in relation to the different topics. The field in which the VWA, and hence the Office for Risk Assessment, works is currently in a state of flux, and that will impact on the enrolment of the programme. Cooperation with other government inspection agencies (authorities), the possible creation of a single inspectorate for the Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality (LNV), development of our relationship with the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) by setting up an “EFSA Focal Point”, cooperation with sister agencies and changes in the knowledge infrastructure are just some of the developments which will shape our work in the coming years.

The programme is based on the Independent Risk Assessment Act which entered into force in 2006. How much we can actually achieve of the Office’s own plans, will ultimately depend on how much leeway we have, financially and otherwise, in a time of cutbacks in the government infrastructure.

Prof. E.G. Schouten
Director Office for Risk Assessment

Summary

The Office for Risk Assessment

The Office for Risk Assessment of the Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority (VWA) provides science based assessments and advise on potential threats to food and product safety, and to animal health and welfare. Its independence is regulated by the Independent Risk Assessment Act passed by Parliament in 2006. Advise under the Act is issued to the Ministers of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality (LNV) and Health, Welfare and Sport (VWS). An Advisory Council established under the Act ensures that the recommendations and assessments are made independently and have a sound scientific basis. In this way risk assessment and risk management are functionally separated within the VWA, while preserving an integral approach. The remit of the Office under the Act and the 2002 VWA Organisational Decree is:

- to carry out (or commission) scientific risk assessments, and issue advises based on the assessments;
- to carry out (or commission) scientific research and to coordinate the research programme.

Advise

The Office provides solicited advise or unsolicited, on its own initiative. Requests for advise may come from government departments, the VWA, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and sister agencies in other Member States. The Office also provides scientific support to other divisions within the VWA. The Office also issues advise as it sees fit, or in response to concerns in society.

Research programme

The integral research programme coordinated by the Office is made up of several components:

- ad-hoc queries to support advise on request, which can often be answered quite quickly;
- strategic research to support its own unsolicited advise. This is proactive research, which generally has a longer time horizon;
- research in support of supervision;
- programming of LNV and VWS research on food and product safety and partly of the research on animal health and welfare.

All the research commissioned by the Office itself ultimately serves to support its risk assessments and subsequent advises.

Procedures

To fulfil its remit, the Office has a team of senior scientists in various fields and support staff (13 fte). Given the volume of work, the Office does not carry out its own research but acts mainly as a knowledge broker with a supervisory and mediating role. It refers its own and others' requests for information to affiliated research institutes (RIVM, RIKILT and CIDC), universities and other institutions. It can also make use of any knowledge and laboratory capacity available within the VWA. Accordingly our advise is provided on the basis of the completed assessments and reports. The aim is to make the best use of national and international scientific networks. The VWA Advisory Group (a board of senior scientists) supports the Office in the performance of its duties.

The programme

An essential component of the 2007-2011 Multi-annual Programme covers the pro-active unsolicited provision of advice. This consists of themes adopted by the VWA Office for Risk Assessment for its own strategic research and resulting advice. The themes are classified in accordance with relevant societal developments. All the themes are concerned with investigating and obtaining timely insight into potential threats that may arise outside our normal field of vision and our traditional network. At the same time it is necessary to base our thinking on uncertainties, which is a skill in itself. Addressing possible future challenges in the best possible way requires creativity, new approaches and sometimes conceptual breakthroughs.

1. Climate change

Impact of (micro and macro) flora and fauna on food safety.

2. Demographic trends and impact of age on risks

Impact of demographic change due to ageing and migration and the special situation of children and elderly.

3. Socio-cultural trends

Impact of changes in lifestyle and behaviour; individualisation and segmentation of society and anti-social behaviour.

4. Globalisation

Decline in transparency in production chains due to increasing movement of goods, people and animals.

5. Changes in production and processing

Impact of production and processing based on new technologies, such as genetic modification, decontamination, nanotechnologies, and, on the other hand, the desire for nostalgic and traditional products.

6. Aiming for sustainability and ethical production

New forms of livestock farming, organic agriculture, recycling and new crop protection methods.

There is also a cross cutting methodological theme concerned with improvement of risk assessment itself. For example, methods for estimating risks, risk-based inspection, cumulative risks, risk perception and acceptance, participatory risk assessment, and risk-benefit analysis.

Implementation

The Multi-annual Programme builds on a modest programme which began a few years ago on a limited budget. The Multi-annual Programme is an ambitious plan to address the themes and topics which the Office for Risk Assessment believes will need attention in the coming years. It has been confirmed in this opinion by national and international scrutiny of the draft document. The independence of the Office for Risk Assessment demands that it can set its own annual priorities among these themes. Its current budget is not sufficient to implement the entire programme, or to commission the necessary volume of strategic research. Efforts will therefore be made to find additional sources of funding, to interest the scientific network in and outside VWA in these themes and to extend cooperation with sister agencies in the EU.

The Multi-annual Programme will be enrolled in annual plans which will also take account of current developments. Where necessary it will be adjusted to tie in with developments elsewhere in the relevant fields.

1 Introduction

The Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority (VWA) is an agency of the Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality (LNV). Its organisation, remit and procedures are laid down in a ministerial decree. In addition to supervision and enforcement the VWA is responsible for risk assessment and coordinating research. These two tasks are assigned to the VWA Office for Risk Assessment. The Office assesses risks and provides independent and scientifically-based advice concerning potential threats to food and product safety. It also advises on animal health and welfare where they impinge upon food safety or public health. Pro-active risk assessment, targeting future risks, is a strategically important component of the Office's duties.

The 2006 Independent Risk Assessment Act regulates the independent implementation of these tasks and independent position of the Office within the VWA (see Chapter 3).

Multi-annual programme for independent risk assessment

The mission, responsibilities and position of the Office for Risk Assessment are presented in Chapter 2 of this multi-annual programme.

Advisory and research procedures are described in chapter 3.

Chapter 4 concerns the priority themes and relevant topics the Office will address in 2007–2010.

Chapter 5 deals with more methodological and horizontal themes. Finally, chapter 6 indicates what we hope to have achieved by 2011 in the Office for Risk Assessment.

Chapter 4 in particular is subject to change. Over the programme period new topics will arise and old topics will be finalised or abandoned. For this reason the entire multi-annual programme will be updated annually. The programme was created by our own experts with input from the VWA and its Advisory Group, the scientific community, LNV and VWS, sister organisations in the EU and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

2 The Office for Risk Assessment

Under the 2002 VWA Organisation Decree, the Office for Risk Assessment has two main tasks:

1. independent scientific risk assessment and advise;
2. directing and coordinating the necessary research.

The first involves assessing the possible risk to public health of threats in the area of food and product safety and making relevant advises. Pro-active assessment of new risks, and issuing unsolicited advises are an important part of this task. The second task involves directing and coordinating an integrated research programme on food and product safety, including the Office's own scientific research in support of the risk assessment, research to support supervision and enforcement of the VWA and research for LNV and VWS.

There is a third task in the pipeline, which is scientific support for supervision. The Office can make a scientific contribution to aspects such as the efficacy of monitoring and other methods used by the regulators.

Position

European citizens want sound scientific assessment of potential public health risks of food and consumer products, so that measures can be taken to manage them. When there are health scares, people want unbiased and clear information. The best way to guarantee this is to ensure that risk assessment is carried out independently and transparently. This has been secured by law in the Netherlands since 2006 (see below).

The Office for Risk Assessment relies on national and international scientific networks for the necessary knowledge and information. The Office acts mainly as a knowledge broker, organising and channelling knowledge and directing research. It draws primarily on knowledge supplied by the VWA's own agencies, RIVM, RIKILT and CIDC.

This multi-annual programme concerns the strategic research required for the pro-active advisory task of the Office. This is where it needs to draw on the knowledge of the broad scientific network and to involve universities and other research institutions in the quest for knowledge. To succeed in its task the Office must have the necessary means at its disposal to actively involve this broad network.

The Office is also the "Focal Point" for EFSA in the Netherlands. The Focal Point will specifically organise cooperation and exchange of information between interested parties in the EFSA and other EU Member States. In the Netherlands the Focal Point will concentrate on three tasks: exchange of information, providing advise on competent organisations and experts, and providing support to the EFSA. The Office for Risk Assessment also represents the Netherlands in the EFSA and in that capacity will also have a say in the working methods and activities of the EFSA with regard to the safety of food and feed.

The Independent Risk Assessment Act

Independence and transparency are regulated in the 2006 VWA Independent Risk Assessment Act. The Office is designated as the risk assessment unit within the VWA, with several guarantees of independence and transparency. Under the Act the Office for Risk Assessment is responsible for advising the Ministers of LNV and VWS either on its own initiative or on request. Requests for advise

may come from LNV and VWS departments, VWA supervision, the EFSA or sister organisations in other Member States. Unsolicited advise is issued on the Office's own initiative, sometimes in response to consumer and public concerns. The Office provides this advise independently, in other words without unauthorised interference from political or other interests. The Act also guarantees maximum transparency: advises are generally published immediately, but in any case within four weeks. This ensures the necessary functional separation of risk assessment and risk management within the VWA as a whole.

Activities

The Office for Risk Assessment has two main tasks:

1. independent scientific risk assessment and advise;
2. directing and coordinating the necessary research.

Risk assessment and advise

The Office accepts requests for advise from government departments, from the VWA (supervision), from the EFSA and from sister authorities. The Office also issues advises on its own initiative. Topics for such unsolicited advise may be chosen in response to public concerns.

Scientific institutions in and outside the Netherlands are commissioned to carry out research to support the advisory work of the Office. They carry out and report on research in close collaboration with the Office. The Office issues advises based on these results to the Ministers of LNV and VWS. Scientific support is also provided to VWA supervision operations and to VWA projects such as the Effective Monitoring Project. Advises are sent to the Inspector General of the VWA. The advises take account not only of objective data, but also other considerations, such as consumer concern. The Office is very keen to identify new, unrecognised or underestimated risks, to investigate them and issue advises at an early stage on possible prevention or control measures.

Research programming

The Office's second major task is research programming. Besides issuing its own knowledge and information requests for the purpose of issuing advise, the Office for Risk Assessment is responsible for coordinating an integrated research programme in food, feed and product safety for the VWA and for the ministries of LNV and VWS.

Products

The Office primarily produces advises and research programmes. Other, derivative products include:

- forecasts and scenario studies;
- trend analyses;
- scientific and other publications.

These products help policy-makers set priorities for risk management measures and contribute to targeted monitoring which effectively manages risk and reduces the burden of inspections.

Transparency

The activities of the Office for Risk Assessment are carried out openly. All the products described above are published on the website or elsewhere, where possible in active collaboration with the Communication Department of the VWA. The transparency of risk assessments and advises is a statutory requirement (under the Independent Risk Assessment Act)

The Office

At the outset it was decided that the VWA Office for Risk Assessment should take the form of a relatively small scientific office which would not carry out research itself, but would play a coordinating and directing role. It can only carry out its duties successfully by organising a scientific panel or network, with the option of commissioning research and knowledge work from other bodies. An independent research budget will be made available for this purpose. The Office will also be able to call on the knowledge and expertise of other parts of the VWA, such as the Inspection Strategy and Communication Directorate, the regional Strategy and Development Departments and the laboratories.

The Office uses the research findings to formulate clear and unambiguous advises and recommendations, which can be used in policy and risk management, and are suitable for broad publication.

Competences

The Office has competences to carry out its activities and fulfil its mission:

Scientific expertise

The Office has many types of expertise available in-house, and can also call on panels or networks of external experts. Knowledge is available in the following disciplines; chemistry, microbiology, toxicology, pharmacology, food sciences, epidemiology, molecular sciences, philosophy, veterinary medicine, nutrition and health and safety.

Clear framing of questions and answers

Research questions, from the policy departments of Ministries, from the VWA Inspection Strategy and Communication Directorate or from the Office itself, are carefully formulated to elicit the relevant knowledge.

Knowledge integration

Scientific knowledge from different fields of expertise are critically assessed and integrated into coherent advises.

“Radar” function

Identifying new risks by observation and other methods such as data mining.

Communication

Capacity to provide clear verbal or written advises in plain language.

Cooperation in networks

The ability to work in multidisciplinary networks to obtain knowledge or information and act as a good commissioning client.

Relations and cooperation

The Office for Risk Assessment has its own support structures in the national and international knowledge network. It has to keep abreast of issues being studied elsewhere and make use of others' experience. This means maintaining good relations within the VWA, with Dutch research institutions, the Ministries of LNV and VWS and various European and international players.

In this way the Office obtains knowledge and input from the VWA itself, the government, the scientific community, advisory boards, civil society and businesses, and internationally from the EFSA, sister authorities and the European Commission.

Above all the Office works with and is building relations with the EFSA and sister authorities; within the Netherlands with the Health Council, the affiliated research institutes, the VWA Advisory Group and of course within the VWA itself. Each of these Dutch organisations has at least some involvement in food and product safety. However, the Office has a statutory duty in this field and differs from the other organisations by virtue of its remit and procedures.

3 Procedures

This chapter explains the procedures for developing the primary products – the advises and the research programme. As mentioned above, the Office’s primary role is to organise and direct.

It generates advise and research with the aid of a network of research institutes and scientists. We look here in turn at the procedure for advise on request, for unsolicited advise, and for research programming.

Advise

The VWA Independent Risk Assessment Act governs the assessment of public health risks and the Director’s advises. It stipulates that advises are addressed to the Ministers of LNV and VWS and that the CEO of the VWA must send these public advises in full and without delay to these ministers. The CEO may separately add recommendations concerning supervision and enforcement aspects. Where relevant the Office also issues internal advises concerning scientific aspects of supervision. (These recommendations are not governed by the Act, and are issued to the CEO).

Before advise can be offered it is generally necessary to assemble knowledge. Available knowledge may be obtained from a literature study. Where new knowledge is required it must be generated. The Office formulates research questions and contracts the work out to research institutions. Sometimes research questions are submitted to experts from the VWA Advisory Group. This is a group of scientific experts who have undertaken to assist the Office for Risk Assessment in the performance of its duties. Dedicated panels can be formed from among the membership to answer research questions on specific subjects.

Advise provided on request

The policy departments and executive services of LNV and VWS, the EFSA and sister authorities can submit requests for advise, which will be processed if the Director of the Office considers that they

are in keeping with the remit of the Office for Risk Assessment. The Office commissions the necessary short-term research from the affiliated institutes, RIVM and RIKILT, which have set up a joint front office for the VWA. Requests for advise taken on by the Office are notified to the coordinating departments of Food Quality and Animal Health (VD) of the Ministry of Agriculture, and Nutrition, and Health Protection and Prevention (VGP) of the Ministry of Health.

Unsolicited advise

The Office may decide to issue advises on its own initiative. These require medium to long term strategic research. They largely concern new issues, new risks and foreseeable problems that require a different approach. The Office for Risk Assessment’s multi-annual programme focuses on this area of its work. Individuals, businesses and interest groups can also bring problems to the attention of the Office for Risk Assessment. The director decides whether or not to issue advises in response to such signals. The coordinating departments are also notified about this type of advise in the preparatory stages.

Utilisation of the advises

Risk assessment and risk management are separate responsibilities, as laid down in the Independent Risk Assessment Act. Ultimately the point is that risk managers need to be able to make the right decisions based on the advises. To provide them with a better service, the Office needs systematic information about how its advises are received by the risk managers, and how practicable they find them. A procedure will be developed to obtain this information.

Research programming

To realise its goals and fulfil its mission, the Office needs to find and exploit available knowledge and information. This demands high standards of knowledge management and the necessary instruments and working relations. The ability to direct or programme research is therefore crucial. It may also involve 'risky' research projects, in the sense that useful results are not guaranteed. When research has to break new ground, the results can be uncertain.

To promote cohesion in government research programming, the Office for Risk Assessment is responsible for coordinating an integrated research programme for LNV, VWS and the VWA in the field of food and product safety, in addition to its own research. The programme will be designed in consultation with relevant departments, as each has its own particular responsibilities. However, the Office will assume a coordinating role to ensure initial and ongoing harmonisation of research.

VWA Office for Risk Assessment Research Programme

The programming process aims to improve the quality of research questions and to guarantee adequate knowledge development. Closer attention will be paid in the coming period to the use made of the knowledge by the VWA. The Office will continue to play a role in improving harmonisation of topics between national and European research.

The programme combines several elements:

Research assignments: research contracts to answer a specific question, issued by the Office to its usual affiliated institutes and sometimes to other suppliers with access to the relevant knowledge. Research is also carried out in the form of doctoral projects to develop knowledge so that the findings can be published in international journals and contribute to scientific underpinning of risk assessment.

Knowledge audits and data mining: these are used to clearly identify and pinpoint knowledge gaps and available knowledge, to make commissioning of research work more targeted and efficient.

Scientific Panels: where knowledge is scattered, scarcely available or controversial, panels of experts from different organisations can sometimes point the way forward.

Foresight studies: the Office for Risk Assessment is concerned not only with acute risks, but also with developments that may lead to future risks. Foresight studies broaden the field of vision and can offer insight into these developments.

Principles for commissioning research projects

The Office will only consider topics and/or knowledge questions for research projects which meet all the criteria below (assuming research is required and the knowledge is not yet available):

- the research topic is clearly related to the VWA's sphere of operations (relevant to its mission, remit, etc.);
- it is in line with the VWA Independent Risk Assessment Act and/or the duties of the Office;
- there is a reasonable suspicion of a risk or potential risk to public health;
- the research must in principle lead to a risk assessment and advises.

Priority criteria

Topics and/or knowledge questions for research must meet one or more of the following criteria:

1. Importance of topic and it is not programmed for research by LNV/VWS. Considerations determining importance are:
 - a. the severity of the risk and/or its potential impact on public health;
 - b. lack of available data or scientific controversy;
 - c. the perception of risks among consumers and the general public;
 - d. the innovative nature of research for risk assessment (e.g.: leads to greatly improved system/method of risk assessment);
 - e. geographic/national reasons: Dutch consumption or behaviour patterns or local (production) conditions can sometimes require investigation on a national scale (e.g. exposure analysis);
 - f. mutually reinforcing signals from diverse sources which require research and/or advise.
2. Support for the VWA in terms of improved supervision and/or compliance and capacity for prevention.
3. Cooperation with other countries and authorities: synergy that can be achieved by linking or synchronising research, and contributing to European food and consumer safety policy.
4. Feasibility and duration of research in relation to the problem and the scale of investment required. Priority is given to research, which can principally produce results within a year.

Integrated research programme

The Office's research programme is part of a larger integrated programme which the Office coordinates. The programme consists of a number of elements:

- ad-hoc queries in support of advise on request, which can generally be answered quite quickly;
- strategic research in support of unsolicited advise: this is pro-active and generally has a longer time horizon;
- programming of LNV and VWS research on food and product safety and some research topics in the field of animal health and welfare.

The programme integrates the food and product safety research goals of the VWA and the Ministries. It is funded by the various government clients (VWS, LNV and the VWA). Research agendas are coordinated accordingly to improve the efficiency of management and knowledge development in support of risk assessment, monitoring and policy. The Office wants to rationalise and harmonise processes that have diverged over time in policy and administration. The Office is currently working out the necessary details of management, conditions and requirements for this. The aim is to set the agenda and provide central administration for collecting the knowledge required by the VWA, LNV and VWS in the short and long term.

VWA-wide access to knowledge and dissemination of knowledge

The Office is working with knowledge institutions to determine the right form and content to make knowledge transfer as simple as possible, so that people are more inclined to find and use the available knowledge. In the coming years, the Office will work to improve transfer of knowledge and knowledge management across the board in the VWA. The aim is to improve access to information and make better use of it, both within the VWA and externally, in the following ways:

- using data from monitoring and enforcement;
- improving access to scientific literature;
- ensuring all VWA staff can find the correct information and have facilities to help in searching;
- ensuring external research contracts and findings are accessible to all staff at the VWA.

4 Themes within risk assessment

This chapter describes medium-term strategic activities aimed at providing unsolicited advice. The motive for offering such advice will often be determined by societal trends. Society and the world around us are constantly changing. Changes can directly or indirectly contribute to serious threats and risks to human and animal health. In devising this multi-annual programme we have considered what significant trends can be observed which may affect the VWA's area of responsibility (food and product safety, animal health and welfare) in the coming years. The aim is to timely identify and flag up dangers

The themes of this programme, which are discussed in the next chapters, were selected on the basis of these changes in our environment. Chapter 4 indicates the topics to be addressed in the coming period. Chapter 5 presents some general and methodological themes. Each theme covers a number of topics which the Office intends to address in the coming period in its research programme and subsequent advice. Of course not everything will be done at once, and given the breadth of some of the themes, activities will have to be tied in with what is happening elsewhere in the world. The subjects are designated as I or II. This indicates the phase of the plan in which they will be dealt with: I indicates 2007 to 2009; II indicates 2010 to 2011.

Each year the multi-annual programme will form the basis for an annual plan detailing the activities for the year ahead. Success will also ultimately depend on the annual budgets available.

Of course, the themes reflect the remit of the VWA as a whole. The table below illustrates the relationship between the planned activities of the Office for Risk Assessment and the major themes of the VWA's plan for 2007.

Table: Relationship between the Office for Risk Assessment's multi-annual programme and the VWA plan for 2007

	Food-safety	Healthy animals	Animal-welfare	Product-safety	Alcohol and tobacco
Changing Climate	X	X			
Age matters	X			X	
No typical consumer	X			X	X
Globalisation	X	X	X	X	
Innovation and safety	X	X	X	X	
Sustainable and ethical	X	X	X		

4.1 The changing climate

There seems to be a gradual upward trend in the average atmospheric temperature. Locally the seasons can seem more extreme and precipitation patterns are changing. These changes affect insect populations and microbiological flora. It is therefore essential to keep advancing our knowledge of the impact of climate change on biodiversity.

Exotic organisms

Tropical and subtropical insects and micro-organisms can migrate to more moderate zones, causing infections and other health problems. Likewise potentially harmful organisms can be transported inadvertently with foods and other products, and can affect the microbiological and chemical quality of food. Growth conditions can affect the production of toxins, and plant varieties containing new phytotoxins can be introduced. At certain temperatures and humidities some moulds can produce mycotoxins which can be harmful to both humans and animals. Shellfish and algae can produce harmful phycotoxins.

New zoonotic threats

Changes in the environment and climate can cause new threats from zoonoses that can have serious consequences for public health, either directly or via the food chain. Pathogenic micro-organisms can be introduced by wild fauna, for example, and these in turn can affect farm animals in the open air.

Signalling new risks associated with climate change is thus very much on the risk agenda for the next few years. The following subjects will certainly receive attention:

1. Food-borne viruses

- methodology for spotting of outbreaks of Norovirus and hepatitis virus (I) ¹;
- impact of high temperature on microbiological food quality (II);

2. Mycotoxins

- frequency and degree of toxin formation due to more vigorous growth of known moulds (I) ;
- new types of mould due to increased temperature, humidity, etc (II);

3. New pathogens

- emerging zoonoses (I);
- other infections (II);

4. New plants and insects

- changes in fauna and flora (biodiversity) that can lead to new threats to the food chain (I).

¹ The subjects are designated as I or II.

This indicates the phase of the plan in which they will be dealt with:
I indicates 2007 to 2009; II indicates 2010 to 2011.

4.2 Age matters

The average age of the Dutch population is bound to rise in the coming decades. The elderly have a special position in society. There are wide variations in the elderly population. Some are fit, enterprising and travel-minded. However, on the other hand also the number of inactive elderly, who have chronic conditions and have difficulty managing on their own. This affects their eating and living habits and the associated risks. Sensory and mobility problems among the elderly and unsuitable products are likely to lead to an increase in accidents.

We must also pay special attention to the younger generation. Injuries and damage to children's health are still high on the prevention agenda. Assessing risks to children requires an understanding of the products they use, their specific behaviour and their susceptibilities. Moreover, many more products are now designed especially for babies and children. We are also increasingly aware that chemical substances can affect young children differently to adults.

Children are not small adults

There is growing evidence that a child's body does not react in the same way as an adult's to chemical substances. This is because the child's body is growing, and rids itself of harmful substances in a different way. This is particularly relevant when setting standards for crop protection products. Moreover, a child has a longer lifetime ahead of it in which to suffer the harmful effects. Therefore there are new and more serious risks for children, and they suffer different effects from chemical substances in food, toys and the environment. Risks to children are also perceived to be worse than they are for adults.

Older people are more susceptible

Many product and safety standards are based on adult males of 24 to 45, rather than on older people who are less able to adapt. For older people, we need to systematically assess the suitability of consumer products in terms of accidents. Hygienic preparation and storage of food can cause problems: resistance decreases with age, making people more susceptible to (food-related) infections. Minimally processed, chilled fresh products are a cause for concern because they may contain pathogens. Deficiencies of some nutrients, such as vitamins and minerals, are increasingly common in the elderly, partly because the need for micronutrients increases with age. A high intake of medicines and supplements among older people contributes to the risk problems. In short the risks surrounding the elderly need urgent extra attention.

In the coming years, we will therefore be giving more attention to children and the elderly in the following specific areas:

1. sensitivity of (young) children

- chemicals: impact on child development (I);
- different/weaker metabolism in children (I);
- children and accidents (II);
- impact of food-borne microbial infections (II);

2. susceptibility of the elderly to

- chemicals (I);
- infections (II);
- interactions with medication (II);

3. supplements

- inventory and analysis of products claiming health benefits which are marketed to the elderly (II);

4. hygiene

- hygiene in the kitchen (I);
- use of minimally processed products (II);

5. accidents

- inventory of products carrying an inherent risk, and the way they are used (I).

4.3 No typical consumer

It is more and more difficult to generalise about consumers. People are far more individual. They make their own choices, and have their own priorities. This individualisation means people feel less responsible for the common good.

People have a range of opportunities. They come into contact with other cultures and lifestyles at home and through foreign travel. Migration brings in new people from other cultures with different priorities. The variety of products has increased enormously, now including “functional foods” and supplements which claim all kinds of health benefits. Eating patterns based on individual choice are also becoming more diverse, and people are exposed to the associated dangers to varying degrees.

Individual sensitivity

There are cultural variations not only in individual eating and lifestyle habits, for example, but also in our biological makeup. We differ in all kinds of hereditary characteristics, not just the visible things like hair and skin colour, but also in the way our bodies react when exposed to certain threats. Thus the risks of exposure are not the same for everyone. These differences lie in the effectiveness of our defence mechanisms, such as our ability to neutralise toxins or overcome infections, or to cope with allergic reactions. These differences may be innate and hereditary or acquired over a lifetime. Differences acquired over time may be related, for example, to nutrition, age, medical history, etc.

All this means that there is no single, uniform risk for the entire population. Hence, there is a need for research in the following areas:

1. exposure via food of specific population groups

- “light” (diet) products, functional foods and supplements (I);
- standards (I);
- high levels of consumption of certain foods (II);

2. nutrition and health

- food allergies (I);
- exploration of the role of the VWA in nutrition and health in the future (I);
- role of nutrition in autoimmune diseases (II);

3. consumer products

- cosmetics and allergies (I);
- dangerous sports (II);

4. multicultural society

- culturally determined risks (II).

4.4 Globalisation

Nowadays the production of consumer products, foods and raw materials need not be tied to a particular place. Production can be moved to low-income countries. There is more and more batch production in temporary chains, mainly outside the EU. There is also more trade via the Internet and shopping channels, in pharmaceutical products (such as growth promoters), food additives, tools and fitness equipment. More live animals are being transported, with repercussions for animal welfare, including increasing trade in exotic animals and pets. There has also been a steep increase in the movement of people (for business and pleasure).

Introduction of pathogens

Large-scale movements of humans, animals and goods increase the risk of the introduction and rapid spread of pathogens. Vectors are particularly significant here. Recent examples of fast-spreading pathogens and vectors include avian influenza and the exotic *aedes* mosquito, a vector of Dengué fever. In certain cases climate change may make matters worse.

Decline in transparency

Globalisation reduces the transparency of the production chain: it is more difficult to trace things, and it is easy to mix products of different origins. The quality can fluctuate. People may resort to undesirable production methods, for example using antibiotics, in order to meet stringent EU requirements, and this can increase the level of risk.

More products are being sold on the Internet, making it difficult to verify their origin, quality and safety.

There is still much uncertainty concerning the impact of globalisation. Further research is therefore recommended, specifically in the following areas:

1. introduction/importation of undesirable products

- infectious animal diseases (including zoonoses) (I/II);
- reinforcing 'pre-arrival' selection and control (I);
- chain analyses (I);

2. transport of live animals

- inventory of effects on animal welfare (I);
- analysis of trade in exotic (pet) animals (I/II);

3. trade in products on the Internet

- inventory and analysis of this sector (II);
- development of a warning system in the event of unacceptable risks (II);

4. undesirable production methods

- use of antibiotics (I).

4.5 Innovation and safety

Technological innovation has led to the introduction of new foods, ingredients and smart packaging, as well as new consumer products. Products based on nanotechnology, genetically modified production animals and micro-organisms in food preparation are just a few examples. Fish farming is growing exponentially as we see an unsettling decline in wild fish stocks in many seas and oceans. On the other hand, there is a counter-movement towards traditional production methods and old-fashioned raw materials, which could be a retrograde step in terms of safety.

New safety aspects

Innovations may be concealing new threats, while old traditional methods can be riddled with long-forgotten dangers. It is therefore important to assess at an early stage whether new products and production methods are safe, or at least as safe as existing technologies. (In principle the burden of evidence lies with the producer). For example, fish grown in open systems may not equate in terms of quality and food safety to fish grown in fully enclosed (recirculating) systems.

For the Office to justify its role, it is important to perform proactive research to produce timely, transparent and objective information about the risks of new developments. Behavioural components of risks will also be studied, so that these can tailor supervision. The following subjects will be studied in the coming years:

1. new food preparation processes

- nanotechnology (I);
- traditional products (I);
- fish farming (I);
- decontamination (II);
- minimal processing (II);

2. consumer products based on nanotechnology

- cosmetics (I);
- products that can lead to the inhalation of nano-particles (II);

3. food contact materials

- intelligent packaging (II);
- diffusion of contaminants (II);

4. biotechnology

- micro-organisms (I);
- production animals (II).

4.6 Sustainability and ethical practice

The aim is to gradually reduce environmentally damaging emissions and raw material and energy consumption to a level which is in equilibrium with the carrying capacity of the earth. Efforts include alternative agriculture systems such as organic and biodynamic agriculture, re-use of waste materials and by-products from food production systems, and the use of recycled water and rainwater for irrigation. There are also improvements in animal housing and husbandry systems aimed at protecting animal welfare.

Quality and safety

Often too little is known about what sustainable and ethical production methods mean in terms of quality and safety. There has not yet been enough research into whether the anticipated benefits are actually being achieved. There may be risks attached to the use of agricultural waste materials, by-products and processed second quality products as raw materials for food or animal feed.

Animal health and welfare

Until now, little attention has been paid to the effects on animal health and welfare of increasing intensification, even in sustainable production. There is still no convincing scientific evidence of the detrimental effects of low grade exposure to harmful contaminants from feed, water or the environment. Due to the short lives of production animals they do not generally present any perceptible clinical symptoms.

A comparative study is required to compare sustainable with conventional production systems for aspects such as animal health and welfare, food quality and food safety. The main areas of study for the coming years will be:

1. animal health

- monitoring systems for general health status (I);
- (new) environmental contaminants (II);

2. animal welfare

- humane animal husbandry and production (II);
- reducing animal testing by using toxicogenomics (II);

3. sustainable alternatives

- waste materials and by-products (I);
- recycling (II);
- organic production methods (II).

5 A clearer view of risks

We need to get a clearer view of the risks attached to food and consumer products and how to manage them, and we need to communicate what we know, including the associated uncertainties. While we must try to reduce risks, safety is still only relative: we can never guarantee absolute safety. The perception of risk among consumers and the general public also plays a role. It is therefore important to weigh risks carefully against each other and against the associated benefits.

This chapter focuses on a few horizontal topics that can help to provide a clearer view of risks and to communicate the information to all the relevant players.

Improving risk assessment

The level of safety or risk, and the associated error margins must be determined and quantified as objectively as possible, based on valid models and empirical data. This applies to both food and product safety. In certain cases epidemiology (epi-based risk assessment) can also be used. The aim is to reduce risks to the consumer from food and consumer products to a fraction of other risks encountered by the general public. It is therefore necessary to compare different risks with each other (risk based judgement).

Excursions above limits

Limits are set to mitigate risks and must be enforced at all times. However, if a limit is exceeded, this does not automatically present a threat to public health, as the limits have broad safety margins built in. The health risk depends on the actual level of exposure of the individual. We need to distinguish here between product limits and intake limits. Whether or not a product limit is exceeded does not necessarily mean that the situation is safe or otherwise:

it depends on the amount consumed, the duration and frequency of the intake, the properties of the substance and on the intake of the same substance from other sources. Exceeding the limit does not necessarily constitute a health risk. The intake limit is often based on the amount a person can safely consume on a daily basis over an entire lifetime. So the actual risk depends on the severity and duration of the excursion above the limit.

Prohibited substances and theoretically harmful but inevitable contamination can now be measured in such small concentrations that their presence as such does not inevitably affect public health. Safety measures need only be taken based on actual health effects. However, if the scale of risk is uncertain, and an absolute zero level is technically possible, then a total ban may be imposed.

Accumulation of risks

Often a risk assessment based on a single chemical substance in a single product is inadequate. The consumer can be exposed to the same substance from different sources, (the “cocktail effect”), for example chemical softeners from plasticizers, sweeteners or preservatives, and sometimes through different uptake routes (mouth, skin, airways). Combination of these exposures should be taken into account. It may also be necessary to consider the background exposure, for example through smoking or environmental pollution. Foods and consumer products often contain combinations of substances whose intake should remain restricted. These may include additives or unintentional contamination, but also many combinations of natural substances. These substances can have similar actions, as in the case of residues of several pesticides in fruit and vegetables, and sometimes one can reinforce the action of another.

Detecting emerging risks

Traditionally the identification and assessment of risks relied on knowledge and expertise available within the food supply chains. However, to anticipate new threats we need to break away from this kind of thinking. First we need to broaden the scope by also looking explicitly at information, knowledge and expertise outside the chains: the broad sweep of a “holistic” host environment analysis. The aim is early detection of potential threats on the horizon and outside our normal field of vision. At the same time, we have to base our thinking on uncertainties, which is a skill in itself. We want to build on the initial insights and ideas gained from preliminary studies, by investigating influential sectors, such as agriculture, public health and welfare, environment and energy. Changes picked up here may give a first indication of potential risk. For this we need monitoring procedures to systematically search, collect, compare and analyse relevant changes within and outside food supply chains. World news and press reports could also be used more systematically as a source of information. We also need a large, ideally heterogeneous, professional network to increase the likelihood of serendipitous information exchange which could bring new risks to light. However, this raises the question of what criteria to apply for a new (serious) risk to be considered in policy development.

Risk acceptance

For the consumer, the risk assessment process is a mystery - risks are often difficult to compare and the criteria are incomprehensible. We want to make this process more transparent for the consumer. It is not enough to publish expert opinion: we need to get closer to the consumer. For this, we need to investigate issues where the process of risk analyses requires input from all the relevant players, including consumers. These are largely issues of uncertain ambiguous risks arising, for example, from new technologies, on which expert opinion is divided.

Weighing the pros and cons

A limited risk may be acceptable when set against a significant health benefit. In other words, you need to include a risk-benefit analysis. Good risk-benefit models are currently being developed. The cost of limiting or eliminating a risk is also an important factor. The cost must be proportionate to the health benefit.

To obtain a better overview of risks, we will research the following topics:

1. Improving risk assessment

- assessment models for accident scenarios with consumer products (I);
- probabilistic models (I);
- risk-benefit analysis and models (I);
- models for transfer of substances from animal feed to products for human consumption (I);

2. Excursions above limits

- application of epidemiological data in risk assessment (I);
- determining food consumption levels for the assessment of food safety (I);

3. accumulation of risks

- combination of substances which have the same action or target the same organ (II);
- taking into account all relevant intake routes (II);

4. Emerging risks

- environmental analysis of production chains (I);
- early-warning system for new risks via information resources (I);
- organisation of periodic “new risk brainstorming sessions” (II);

5. consumer participation

- involving consumers in risk assessment (II);
- ethics and risk assessment (II);

6. support for inspection and supervision

- Underpinning of effective inspection (I);
- sound scientific sampling strategies (II);
- risk profiles for import controls (to improve information position) (I);
- contaminant risk profiles of Dutch farmland (II);
- unethical practice on the part of producers and traders (moral hazards) (II).

6 The Office for Risk Assessment in 2011

Finally, we look briefly at our ambitions for the period of the programme, and what we hope to have achieved by the end. Of course, we cannot yet foresee the impact on our work of the changing environment described in the foreword.

By 2011 the Office for Risk Assessment should be well-known to stakeholders and the public as an independent authority in risk assessment.

To this end by 2011 the Office should:

- have access to sources of information, scientific networks and research facilities which facilitate sound, pro-active risk assessment;
- use knowledge and data collected in the course of VWA monitoring;
- apply nationally and internationally recognised, state-of-the-art risk assessment methods;
- plan and co-finance research projects to detect and investigate new or underestimated risks;
- issue advises to be used in policy and implementation for risk management which effectively controls risks and prevents an undue burden of inspections.

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